

APPLICATION OF SPANNING TREES IN CANCER CELLS

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Abstract:

Goal: In this paper purpose to develop a classification method that combines some details for distinguishing cancer cells from tissue on spanning tree in model. Method: Depth First search (DFS) traversal of a graph is analogous to pre order traversal of an ordered tree and next Breadth-first search (BFS) traversal of a graph is an analogous to level by level traversal of an ordered tree. The elaborated Greedy Choice is to pick the smallest weight edge that doesn't cause a cycle in the MST then consider the Dark black line edges cancer cells travel distance to a affect the next cells and vertices is human cells. Conclusion: An MSF based Kruskal's Algorithm method was proposed and evaluated for distinguishing cancer cells from tissue on spanning tree in model.

Introduction:

Graphs serve as mathematical model to analyze successfully many concrete real world problems. The field of medicine is one of the most fruitful and interesting areas of applications of graph theory. Application of spanning trees in many department and real life situations have been studied many researchers. In this paper, by using notion of maximum spanning tree, we apply graph theory through the well know Celluler's approach for medical diagnosis and we exhibit the technique with cancer cell disease case study. Cancer cell disease in one of the most deathly ailments known to mankind due to its high death rate (up to 90%) conveying with the disease. Basic in cancer cells: A cancer cells transitional period of theories trying to replace the ancient theories followed but was quickly replaced by a period based on the cellular theory, proposing that both of normal and cancerous cells come from cells of common origin. There were a series of new techniques for diagnosis and treatments from the mid-19th century and onward. Lat of times, further advances within this prolonged cellular period have been made based on new insights into genetics and other scientific fields.

Basic Definition:

- A tree is a connected acyclic graph.

Example:

Minimum Spanning Tree:

The minimum spanning tree of a weighted graph is a set of $n - 1$ edges of minimum total weight which form a spanning tree of the graph.

Maximum Spanning Tree:

The maximum spanning tree is a spanning tree of a weighted graph having maximum weight. It could be computed by negating the weights for the every edge and applying term in Kruskal’s algorithm.

Path Graph:

A path graph is a graph that can be drawn so that a of its vertices and edges lie on a single straight line.

Example:

Weight of a Binary Tree:

A binary tree that has n leaves with the weight w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n assigned to the leaves is said to be a binary tree for the weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n . The weight of a binary tree for the weights w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n is $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i l(w_i)$.

Where $l(w_i)$ denote the path length.

Depth First Search: (DFS)

Let $G = \langle V, E \rangle$ be a simple connected graph with the attribute of n vertices. Arrange the elements of V as ordered list v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n .

Let v denote the vertex that is presently examined. Let T denote the spanning tree obtained as a rooted tree by applying DFS algorithm.

Algorithm:

Step 1 (Initialization)

Let $v \leftarrow v_1$ and $T = \{v_1\}$, (v_1 is a root of the tree T obtained in the final step).

Step 2 Select the smallest i such that $\{v, v_i\} \in E$ and v_i has not been visited earlier. If no such v_i exist go to step: 3 Otherwise,

- Attach an edge (v, v_i) of T
- Let $v \leftarrow v_i$
- Return to step: 2

Step 3 If $v = v_1$, then T is rooted spanning tree with v_1 as its root.

Step 4 If $v \neq v_1$, back track v , If p is the parent of v , Let $v \leftarrow p$ and go to step 2.

Breadth First Search (BFS):

Breadth-first search traversal of a graph is an analogous to level by level traversal of an ordered tree. Else the traversal has just visited a vertex v , so that next visits all the vertices adjacent to v . Putting the vertices adjacent to these in a waiting list to be traversed after all vertices adjacent to v have been visited. For Breadth first algorithm a queue is needed instead of stack. Queue is a list in which all insertions are made of one end called the back and all deletions are made at the other end called the front. Queues are referred as-first in, first out.

This algorithm is used to find a path which uses least number of edges that is the shortest path.

Step 1 Label the vertex α with 0, set $i = 0$.

Step 2 Find all unlabeled vertices in G which are adjacent to vertices labeled i . If there are no such vertices then z is not connected to ' α '. If there are such vertices, label them $i + 1$.

Step 3 If z is labeled, go to step 4. If not increase i to $i + 1$ and go to step 2.

Step 4 The length of the shortest path from α to z is $i + 1$, then stop.

Once the length of the shortest path is found from BFS, We use the back tracking algorithm to find the shortest path from α to z . This algorithm uses the label $\lambda(v)$ which are generated in BFS algorithm.

Back Tracking Algorithm (BTA):

Step 1 Set $i = \lambda(z)$ and assign $v_i = z$

Step: 2 Find a vertex u adjacent to v_i and with $\lambda(u) = i - 1$. Assign $v_{i-1} = u$.

Step: 3 If $i = 1$, then stop, if not then decrease i to $i - 1$ and go to step: 2.

Example Obtain a BFS- spanning tree graph in the given graph.

Kruskal's Algorithm:

In Kruskal's Algorithm, there be creating a MST by picking edges one by one. The elaboration of Greedy Choice is always to pick the smallest weight edge that does not cause a cycle in the MST CONSTRUCTED so far.

We construct a spanning subgraph H at each iteration. We start with $E(H) = \Phi$, and n components of H . (As $E(H) = \Phi$, every vertex of G is a component of H). At each iteration we consider the next cheapest edge and so on. The algorithm stops after

$(n - 1)^{th}$ iteration, as at the stage the spanning graph H is a tree.

Algorithm:

Step: 1 Choose an edge e_1 such that $w(e_1)$ is as small as possible.

Step: 2 If the edges $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_i\}$ have been chosen, then choose an edge e_{i+1} from $E(G) \setminus \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_i\}$ in such a way that

- The spanning subgraph H whose $E(H) = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_i, e_{i+1}\}$ is acyclic.
- $w(e_{i+1})$ is small as possible subject to (i).

Step: 3 Stop when Step: 2 cannot be implemented further.

The spanning graph T produced by kruskal algorithm is optimal.

Example Consider the below graph. Where vertices are cancer cells and edges is cancer cells is traveling to path of other cells.

Consider the Dark black line edges cancer cells travel distance to a affect the next cells and vertices is human cells. Consider the graph.

Reverse Deleting Algorithm:

- It is the reverse from of the kruskal’s algorithm.
- Start with all edges.
- Delete the longest edge.
- Continue deleting longest edge as long for every nodes are connected and no cycles.

Algorithm Example:

Conclusion:

In this paper, we presented the graph theory of spanning trees in the field of human diseases diagnosis. We improve some new notions such as complement of max product of spanning tree based of reference function. At the conclusion, the cancer cell affected persons should be given conscious of how it has affected the human body.

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